

DIGNITY AS A SOCIAL VIRTUE AND LEGAL RIGHT: TOWARDS A SOCIO-POLITICALLY CONSCIOUS AND HUMANITARIAN VIEW

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Abstract

This article proffers a critical appraisal of South Africa's constitutional perspective of the right to human dignity, fundamentally considerate of past injustices, upon which the post-1994 dispensation's natural socio-political obligations are predicated. The article reaffirms the strength found in the notion of human dignity as an essential doctrine and yardstick in the interpretation, application, enforcement and development of human rights and the wellbeing of humans in general. However, it stresses that redressing the past injustices requires going beyond the constitutionally entrenched norms. That, the struggle against apartheid was predominantly predicated on restoring dignity among the oppressed proletariat, achieving a better life, and not about producing the so called 'best constitution' in the world. That is, the rights narrative which does nothing to foster a social commitment and humanitarian progress is fundamentally hollow, and thus will not deliver the dream of a better life for all. It is however asserted that South Africa has succeeded in embedding the strong norms at the bedrock of the social and legal systems. Nonetheless, these norms have not meaningfully infused into social realities towards realising human wellbeing. This has been and continues to be hampered by lack of political commitment by state functionaries, and somewhat wrong choice in policy directives, exacerbated by external influences.

Keywords: *human dignity, human wellbeing, good and better life, social development, humanitarians.*

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1. Introduction and context

Section 1(a) of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996 (*hereinafter, the Constitution*) provides that 'South Africa is founded on the values of human dignity, the achievement of equality and advancement of human rights and freedoms'. The staunch protagonists of human rights have argued that this constitutional injunction established South Africa as a rights respecting state (Mandela, 1996; Sarkin, 1999; Hongju Koh, 1999; Sunstein, 2001; Liebenberg, 2010; Human Rights Watch, 2014), but understandably, did not provide a clear theoretical explanation and application of this dogmas to real life social situations.

Whereas the crafters of South Africa's post-1994 democratic dispensation opted to approach the concept of dignity from a rather more legal or semilegal viewpoint, this article seeks to approach dignity from a socio-political and humanitarian perspective, with the view towards observing and reasoning about dignity as a multi-faceted value, whose prime predication is on preserving human worth, more than embedding legal norms. Of course, the post-apartheid state relied on the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948 (UDHR), which states that 'the recognition of the inherent dignity of and of the equal and inalienable rights of all members of the human family is the foundation of freedom, justice and peace in the world'. Indeed, the UDHR played a pivotal function in universalizing the utilisation of dignity in human rights discourses (McCrudden, 2008:655), hence a variety of constitutions, including South Africa's, entrenched it as a right and a foundational value. And, according to Hayry (2004:7), this quote from the UDHR presupposes an inherent connection between rights and the concept of dignity, and freedoms and better life, which is the prime object of this article. That is, to proffer a renewed perspective on why dignity is central to both legal and moral application of the post-apartheid Constitution, and why there is a need for a socially and politically conscious construction of norms that resonate ideals of ushering in a better life for all in accordance with the Aristotelian perspective, depicting moral correctness and probity in humans.

It is worth mentioning that the contemporary South Africa suffers a greater deal of social discontent, which should be recognised as one of major threats to social stability and humanitarian peace. Social discontent is often perceptible when citizens, especially the proletariat, resort to extraordinary methods to survive, especially when they feel they are left with no chance to realize their internal and external capabilities, and that there is nothing enabling them to enjoy their human dignity, both as a constitutionally entrenched right and as a virtue of life. Liebenberg (2002:160) has argued that the strategic inclusion of socio-economic rights in the Constitution was essentially to serve as an anti-poverty initiative. It was envisioned that this would assist the indigent people, in the main, protect and advance their basic socio-economic needs and interests, with the view towards restoring their dignity. This entailed going beyond paper promises. Anyway, what purpose is achieved when admirable rights narratives only serve to safeguard the interest of the capitalist rich men? This becomes a common question when the connected political elite and the bourgeoisies continue to try to preserve the ancient traditions of affording dignity according to rank or hierarchy in society.

2. Rationale and methodology

According to Fox (2001: 275), the concept of dignity is socio-politically sensitive and is geared towards strengthening those forces which bring harmony and social stability amongst people. Thus, I begin on the premise of an assumption that dignity represents social good, moral correctness, human welfare, social stability and legal entitlement. Further, that the crux of dignity, as a virtue, is that it is a tool through which to measure or evaluate human discipline and commitment to humanitarian wellbeing. Thus, I ask the question, how can we fix the apartheid's historic destruction of humane moral understandings predicated on the principle that all humans are worthy of respect and good life?

The object of this article is to contribute some insightful thoughts into discourses that have concentrated on the notion of dignity as a human rights issue, which, as emphasised by Fyfe (2007:1), has been given added impetus by the international community's willingness to insert it in a variety of legal texts, inclusive of international treaties, regional instruments, domestic constitutions and various statutory enactments. It illustrates that owing to its rich

historical and philosophical tradition (Bostrom, 2009:84), the notion of dignity as a virtue, can help us properly situate and safeguard the wellness of humans without regard to rank or societal hierarchies of humans. The article derives strengths from the Aristotelian perspective of dignity, and seeks to illustrate how humanity thrives when there is an appreciation of an intrinsic interdependence of humans, and the context of a better life. It further demonstrates the essence of protecting dignity, and the core elements necessitating such protection. Further, that there is an inherent need to explain the role of dignity, both as a right and virtue in reshaping social relations and human wellbeing. I stress that as a virtue, the concept of dignity requires of us, a strict amount of moral reasoning which carries components or dimensions that are predicated on recognizing, as an obligation, an understanding that every human being must attain minimum essentials of life in order to attain good life. As a right, I emphasize that dignity serves to remind the state and private individuals alike, that human worth is an inalienable value, which cannot be traded for anything, and thus law, law enforcers and judicial officers ought to protect it at all times.

The article combines both doctrinal and theory based analysis to explain the missing link between South Africa's social dynamics and the law in the Constitution, towards constructing a new view with regards to the perception of the law and human wellbeing. The article is somewhat abstract in nature, and proffers a supplementation to thoughts propagated in Rapatsa (2015), on dignity as the yardstick in the interpretation of rights, and in Rapatsa and Makgato (2016), on dignity as an epitome of social transformation.

3. Theoretical framework

An Aristotelian perspective about happiness and an ideal life notably does have an overarching effects on the meaning of quality of life and or good life, which derives impetus from dignity as a virtue. In terms of this approach, it entails that virtue in dignity is seen when certain specific elements are present. For instance, such virtuous rudiments may include having access to basic necessities of life such as food, clothing, shelter, education, water and so forth, and I venture to say, being able to participate in the country's socio-political developments.

Thus, Aristotle's conceptualisation of an 'ideal life' proffers pragmatic tools through which to explain South Africa's social realities afflicting the poor, and the middle class strata, who often turn out to be the 'previously disadvantaged delusionals', and their constantly diminishing prospects of realizing human dignity. According to Aristotle, the ideal life circumstances for a human being are those which afford humans 'freedom' to contemplate as much as they can, given the inevitable physical, emotional, and social demands of human nature, and only then, can humans achieve absolutely ideal life (Lawrence, 1993:14). This entails that social elements which determine the wellbeing of humans also serve as determinants of the realisation of dignity. Somewhat, this is resonated by Sherman (1993:298), when stating that dignity as a virtue is fundamental to society because it cultivates a focus on the fact of common doing, as opposed to a more focus on self. Altogether, Aristotle's view stresses that the good has rightly been declared to be that at which all things aim (Smith, 1986:9), and this is only achievable when humans retain their original state of nature, a sense that their being is equally worthy of respect and protection. This is particularly important because Aristotle's conception of happiness and wellbeing presupposes that virtue would be rendered worthless if happiness is not perceived as the end of action. That is, our interactions should clearly demonstrate that we strive to do good,

which somewhat come across as a moral obligation in terms of which humans owe unto each other, some level of protection.

For purposes of this article, discussions on human dignity takes two forms; the sociological, and political viewpoints. The social movement would argue that human dignity stems from the worth of humans which accrues to a person upon birth and becomes inalienable, further requiring that humans be afforded dignity, and social amenities that enable them to assert their worth (Rapatsa, 2015:44). It prevails and obligates the state to ensure that it is realized within reasonable constitutional tenets. The political, which largely informed legal developments, is premised on the UNDR which gave birth to various international promulgation of statutory framework protecting human dignity. This resonate the objectives of the Declaration on the Right to Development of 1989, whose primary intention was ensuring that third generation of rights are viewed as a pre-condition for asserting human dignity. Thus, human dignity encompasses social rights, legal and political rights and economic rights. These tenets constitute its founding imperatives, which the state power must respect and protect (Starck, 2002). Immanuel Kant has also shared some insights on the concept of dignity, by asserting that is an inviolable property of all human beings, which gives the possessor the right never to be treated simply as a means, but always at the same time as an end (Schroeder, 2010). Further that humans occupy a special place in creation, holding an inherent worth of dignity which cannot be comparable to that of other creatures (Rachels, 1986). Kant posited that humanitarianism and dignity are such designated values without any equivalent (Shell, 2008). Kant theorized human dignity as ‘an absolute inner worth’ that exists inside every rational person, that no one is permitted to destroy it (Gregor, 1996). Dworkin (1993) believes that dignity is inherently linked with the capacity for self-respect, self-worth and consciousness.

4. The Constitution and its humanitarian outlook

South Africa’s historical socio-economic deprivations culminated in the drafting of the Constitution to consider including mechanisms that would be people sensitive and more biased to their wellbeing and welfare. This was primarily to ensure that the Constitution is meaningfully responsive towards resolving happiness problems faced in ordinary political lives (Sunstein, 2001: 3). As a result, chapter 2 containing the Bill of Rights, constructing a system of vertical and horizontal relations between the state and private persons, and the state and private entities (De Vos, 2002:243), in terms of which each bears own entitlements and obligations. This has resulted in the inclusion of section 27, which entrenched socio-economic rights. This is what is understood as a strategic transformative humanitarian disposition, which is fundamentally geared towards alleviating and/or eliminating human suffering in order that the Aristotelian perspective of happiness and good life may be achieved with ease. The essence of transformative humanitarian ideal is founded on the necessity to serve humanity better, particularly to preserve human worth, dignity. However, whether this has been realized thus far is a matter of contentious debate. But what is clear is the fact that section 7(2) of the Constitution requires the state to respect, protect, promote and fulfil all these values, with emphasis on safeguarding the dignity of persons. Notable dignity-orientated socio-economic rights include the right to education, health care, housing, food and water and right to social assistance. In a nutshell, a determination of fulfilling minimal social and economic needs, conforms to norms of humanitarianism, whose central objectives, among others, is to safeguard dignity in persons.

It is indubitable that indeed the Constitution established a commendable normative and institutional framework that served humanitarian objectives better. In the circumstance, it

requires government to progressively provide most basic amenities of life to its citizens within its available resources. In many instances courts preferred reasonableness approach over minimum core arguments. This minimum core approach, although predicated on establishing a minimum legal content, it also has far-reaching effect as a needs-based normative essence as far as it concerns the right to life, survival and access to fundamental needs. That, it is a value-based core, which seeks to restore human dignity, while advancing equality and human freedoms (Young, 2008). Nevertheless, it is inescapable to question whether specific dignity-based socio-economic rights have been realized in practical terms.

Access to social assistance is a prime example of dignity based legal entitlement. The Constitution obligates the state to provide social assistance to indigent people who lack the adequate means to support themselves. This is posited in accordance with the ‘minimum core’ requirement which essentially state that the minimum essentials be met. The right to social assistance was canvassed in *Khosa & Others v Minister of Social Development* 2004 (6) SA 505 (CC): 111, and *Saletla Mahlaule & Another v Minister of Social Development* CCT13/3 (2004) where it was emphasized that providing social assistance constitute a crucial means enabling people realize their dignity and equality. Further that measures put in place should enable the reach by everyone as stipulated in the Constitution.

On the list also features the right to adequate housing. It was delivered in *The Government of the Republic of South Africa v Grootboom* 2000 (11) BCLR 1169 (CC): 14, 15 & 23. This case declared that people living under squalid conditions are effectively deprived of their dignity, and often experience humanitarian threats daily. It was held that the state ought to provide adequate housing to people in desperate need. This is perceived as giving real meaning and substance to the foundational values advancing transformative agenda of socio-economic rights jurisprudence (Liebenberg, 2010). Yacoob J stressed that to report progress on the right of access to housing, imperatives on the right to dignity and equality should be given attention. The unfortunate tale is that Mrs Grootboom died eight years later, yet homeless, penniless and with compromised dignity.

Water is life itself, and thus there is fundamental need to situate its significance on the dignity concept. Section 27(1)(a), the right to adequate water provision, was dealt with in *Mazibuko & Others v the City of Johannesburg & Others* (CCT 39/09) [2009] ZACC 28; 2010 (4) DA 1 (CC). The court adopted the reasonableness approach, with specific focus on socially and value-based analysis underscoring human dignity. The city was ordered to take reasonable measures, progressively, to ensure adequate provision of the right to water. Heleba (2011:25) has stressed that the judgment epitomized sensitivity to the indigent people, recognizing the use of human rights as a means to advance social transformation (Bond and Dugard, 2008).

It is clear that courts have actively occupied responsive activist stance in attempting to protect dignity of humans as a means to realizing happiness and good life.

5. Transforming the past-present, bettering the future

The above jurisprudential reflection is testament of a variety of tenets. In the main, it stresses that the post-apartheid transition brought about a distinct legal and political construction of the law, which was accompanied by a strong human rights outlook. This culminated in a legal system grounded on the supremacy of the constitution, which embedded human dignity at the centre of humanitarian and human rights discourses. This constitutional supremacy carried with it, the agenda of Transformative Constitutionalism (TC) which is founded on fundamental epitomes espousing social justice and substantive

justice in social, economic and political realities, and building a nation grounded on protecting democratic values and fundamental human rights. It aims at re-establishing a society that serves humanity better. Klare (1998:146) conceptualised the TC as a ‘long-term project of constitutional enactment, interpretation and enforcement committed to transforming a country's political, legal and social institutions, and power relations in a democratic, participatory and egalitarian direction’. It is modelled on redressing past injustices and building a better future (Langa, 2006; Bohler-Muller, 2007), ensuring substantive equality and, in the main, protection of human dignity (Moseneke, 2007), which enriches the human rights discourse as a means to greater social ends. It implored state to devise and implement measures to redress the legacy of apartheid, whilst also addressing modern forms of subordination that hinder realization of human dignity to vulnerable groups (Liebenberg, 2010).

The TC protects dignity through its holistic vision of encompassing social transformation, taking into account the known history of unjust legal system which inhibited development of human rights (Sarkin, 1998). The purpose is to end historic human rights violations that severely trampled on the dignity of persons (Ndangwa, 2004). The institutionalized racially repressive legal system had perpetuated class-based segregation that rendered humanitarian survival impossible. Consequently, threats on humanitarian wellbeing soared owing to abject poverty and social deprivations. Mbeki (2007) reiterated that the need to end apartheid was intensified with the view of restoring dignity of persons. It hopes to achieve this by inculcating a culture of respect of the Bill of Rights, while obligating the state to promote and faithfully observe international human rights norms (Mandela, 1996).

6. A practical conception of dignity

Although the concept of dignity runs without a universally embraced definition, there seem to be some global consensus with regards to the humanist essentials it conveys, at least, from both human rights and socio-political perspectives. Because dignity is traded as a hallmark of the rights and wellbeing narratives, a common understanding on what it means is indispensable. This can be achieved through ordinary description. At the face value, it connotes human worth, an idea that no one should be subjected to abuse, degradation, torture, harassment and/or neglect of any kind which threatens one’s dignity. It is concerned with respecting and protecting personhood, which justifies an exceptional position of man in nature’s creation, whose entitlements feeds off the outrage of the humiliated at the violation of one’s dignity (Habermas, 2010). I venture to dispose dignity in three ways, in an attempt to locate the metaphysical nature and strength of this concept within the context of what and how it advances humanitarian interests.

6.1 Dignity as a social edifice

In this context, I present dignity as a moral construct, which creates social obligations among humans to protect each other. That is, when humans appreciate that they owe unto each other, an intuitive moral obligation to respect and protect humankind, that constitute the predication of dignity. In this context, I rely on moral reasoning to posit dignity as a shared social value. As a social edifice, dignity is a conception which holds that man is a social creature of dignity, with inalienable entitlement to infinite respect (Miller, 1968:27). This approach resonates Kant’s perspective that dignity is a moral postulate (Fyfe, 2007:12), which entails that the violation of this imperative constitute infringement of man’s social freedoms, without which humanitarian survival is compromised. It has also been observed

that dignity is more concerned with individual autonomy, which constitute its ethical element, and further, the life and liberty of the individual which is concerned with one's ability to pursue own goals without interference (Neal, 2012:28).

6.2 Dignity as a legal entitlement

The crafters of laws promulgate legal instruments that are premised on regulating the conduct of natural and juristic persons, especially because there ought to be an appreciation that everyone's right to self-determination must be recognized and protected. Therefore, it is crucial to appreciate the essence of regulating human conduct, especially in the context of what human beings desire from such legal instruments. Thus, dignity is a legal norm, which informs both the normative and institutional frameworks established through statutory methods. It is for this reason that dignity ought to also be understood as a principle which has significance on the egalitarian framework of human rights, which is that of being a high moral tool consisting of a set of rights that guarantee a high degree of inviolability and respect (Toscano. 2011:5). In the main, dignity is central to every democratic society because it determines how state power is exercised towards citizens, while being the first edifice of human rights (Glensy, 2011:68).

6.3 Dignity as a humanitarian virtue

From a humanitarian perspective, dignity is viewed as an ideological doctrine which provides theoretical guidance in terms of what ought to serve as determinants of good life. In terms of the Aristotelian perspective, it means happiness as determined by the wishes of an individual. On the other hand, Kant's perspective, which emphasises the intrinsic worth of humans, considers dignity as a dogma which has been fundamental in guiding humanitarian actors in carrying out humanitarian work. It is for this reason that humanity and preservation of human dignity are part and parcel of significant principles of humanitarian work. therefore, the essence of dignity is that of fostering an uninterrupted continuation of life filled with dignity (Rapatsa, 2016:13).

7. Conclusion

This article set out to contribute some conceptual clarity on the notion of dignity. It has ascertained that although the constitutional entrenchment of dignity as a right was essentially legalistic, such inclusion has potential to produce numerous salient socio-political benefits which would profoundly influence South Africa's human rights and socio-political developments in practice. The Aristotelian perspective on happiness was used to validate, at least subjectively, that dignity requires us to consider others as worthy as we perceive ourselves. Effectively, a distinct socio-legal connotation of the notion of dignity has been ascribed, which is imperative in determining societal social stability and human wellbeing. Most importantly, the article has also demonstrated that the strength of the notion of dignity lie in morally admirable acts of humans. That is, dignity is a concept of intuitive moral reasoning. And, as a social virtue, it has the capacity to build strong human relations which breeds societal social peace and justice. As a right, it helps society fathom the role of the law in harmonising humans and regulating human conduct, which is that no acts must harm the worth of humans, and their dignity in particular. It is asserted that dignity ought to be acknowledged as a substantive basic norm (Neal, 2014:43) which is necessary to justify

every moral and legal reasoning of any action or decision that affect humanity. In the end, the normative validity of dignity lies in the fact that it, at best, reflects the essence of humanity.

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